

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B034
 Date: 25 Jul 2004
 Take Off 09:56:48 16:39:49
 Landing: 15:08:38 18:53:46
 Flight Time 5h11m50 2h13m57

Trials Instructions: ITOP - Interception of processed North American pollution to the east of the Azores and contrasting African air.

Operating Area: A box bordered from the TMA and 36 24N, 20W; 37N 30W; 31N; 31N, 20W (surface to FL250)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Monks	Leicester University
4	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
5	Core Chemistry/FWVS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
6	HCHO	Graham Mills	UEA
7	PTR-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
8	PAN/TDL/PSAP	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
9	PERCA	Mark Jacob	Leicester University
10	Peroxides	Brian Bandy	UEA
11	WAS	Lisa Whalley	Leeds University
12	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
13	Noxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
14	Mission Scientist 2	Ally Lewis	York University
15	Refuel Engineer	Andrew Boardman	Avalon Aero
16	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
17			
18			

Track Plot:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B034
 Date: 25th July 2004
 Project: ITOP
 Location: Horta, Azores

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095648		T/O	0.0 kft	269	
100020					ASPs opened
100103	100515	Run 1	5.0 kft	122	Wet chem calcs
100810					PSAP flow on
101110	105953	Run 2	13.0 kft	117	
101250					end J-W cal.
101357					TWC reset
101507					video rec. start
101550					HORACE crash
102620	102750				loss of data, HORACE ok
104850					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
110000	111007	Profile 1	13.0 - 22.0 kft	130	1000ft/min
111022	112022	Run 3	22.0 kft	136	
112028	114037	Profile 2.1	22.0 - 4.8 kft	134	1000ft/min
114037	115116	Profile 2.2	4.8 - 0.10 kft	136	500ft/min
115130	115629	Run 4	0.1 kft	132	
115751	120356	Profile 3	0.1 - 3.0 kft	222	500ft/min
120000					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
120537	121234	Run 5	3.0 kft	055	
121403	123144	Profile 4.1	3.0 - 15.0 kft	227	1000ft/min
121930		interrupt P4.1	8.0 kft	221	1000ft/min
122128		recommence P4.1	8.0 kft	048	1000ft/min
122658		interrupt P4.1	13.0 kft	048	1000ft/min
122904		recommence P4.1	12.9 kft	220	1000ft/min
124227	125227	Run 6	15.0 kft	016	
125423	125920	Profile 4.2	15.0 - 19.0 kft	223	
125928	130929	Run 7	19.0 kft	217	
125940					PSAP flow off
130210					PSAP flow on
130355					PSAP flow off
130430					PSAP flow on
130535					PSAP flow off
130755					PSAP flow on
					ice obscuring FFC
131019					PSAP flow off
131138	131507	Profile 4.3	19.0 - 22.0 kft	038	1000ft/min
131248					PSAP flow on
131338					PSAP flow off
131448					PSAP flow on
131515	132727	Run 8	22.0 kft	040	
131720					PSAP flow off
131850					PSAP flow on
132226		interrupt run	22.0 kft	042	
132407					PSAP flow off
132416		recommence run	22.0 kft	217	
132451					PSAP flow on
132615					PSAP flow off
					tail anti-ice on
132630					PSAP flow on
132919	133537	Profile 4.4	22.0 - 25.0 kft	039	
133146		interrupt P4.4	24.0 kft	046	
133300					PSAP flow off
133431		recommence P4.4	24.0 kft	220	

133600					PSAP flow on
133605	133910	Run 9	25.0 kft	221	
133727					tail anti-ice off FFC still obscured
133921	134721	Profile 4.5	25.0 - 32.0 kft	221	
135000					FFC improving
135011	135653	Run 10	32.0 kft	319	
135700	135955	Run 11	32.0 kft	038	
140534	141659	Run 12	32.0 kft	302	
141713	142352	Profile 5	32.0 - 25.0 kft	302	
142404	143356	Run 13	25.0 - 25.1 kft	300	
142800					SATCOM call, CCM to DFL
143403	145200	Profile 6	25.0 - 8.0 kft	298	
145207	150205	Run 14	8.0 kft	298	
150838		Land	0.03 kft	172	Santa Maria
151230	GPS final posn 36 58.46N 25 09.96W				
151442	INU final posn 36 57.86N 25 09.38W				
151540	INU to align				
162020	INU to Navigate				
163949		T/O	0.0 kft	171	Santa Maria
164240					PSAP flow on
164349	171933	Run 15	5.8 kft	331	QNH 1021 at Punta Delgada JW cal finished video rec. start
165105					FL060
165340					
172034	172340	Run 16	5.8 kft	354	
172356	172638	Profile 7	5.8 - 4.3 kft	356	
172645	173814	Run 17	4.3 kft	353	
173415					PSAP flow off
173715					PSAP flow on
174020	174526	Run 18	4.3 kft	267	
174539	174853	Profile 8	4.3 - 5.8 kft	272	
174900	181618	Run 19	5.8 - 6.0 kft	273	FL060
181838	184443	Run 20	6.0 kft	130	
184025					PSAP flow off
184200					PSAP flow on
184915					PSAP flow off
185346		Land	0.0 kft	269	Horta
185722	Final GPS posn. 38 31.26N 28 42.98W				
185800	Final INU posn. 38 31.26N 28 43.66W				

B034 Track 25-JUL-04

SHANWICK OCEANIC
CTA (A) / EGGX FIR
(Unct'l below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA OCEANIC
CTA (A) / LPPO FIR (G)
(Unct'l below FL55)
NAT-RVSM AIRSPACE FL290-FL410

SANTA MARIA RADIO	
NAT A	NAT E
3016	2962
5598	6628
8906	8825
13306	11309
17946	17946
VHF	
127.90	132.07
SELCAL	
① 426302	

SANTA MARIA CONTROL
132.15 (TMA)
Above FL 155

RNAV required in all European upper airspace. Should aircraft not be RNAV equipped/nor operational, include a "Negative-RNAV" report immediately after the aircraft call sign on initial contact on an ATC frequency.

LISBON AIRPORT
on Espichel VORTAC and any tracks via DIRMA Int. operators conducting flight in Area OCA north of 37°N on to Santa Maria OAC. To be requested during ...

cross the EUR/SAM and insert the entry/exit active estimated crossing the crossing of each of s into the FPL item 18.

AL PERFORMANCE 10NM (RNP10) & 3-BER TECHNIQUE
51 and following.
true Mach No. The ATC clearance must include ...
has to be stated in the flight plan by pilots ...
wing ATS routes:
27.4) - Fortaleza VORDME
37.5) - Natal VORDME
30.3) - Mossoro VORDME
21.5) - Noronha VORDME
37.5) - Noronha VORDME
their assigned Mach numbers unless a specific ...
ATC unit if an immediate temporary change in the ...

CANARIES RADIO	
NAT E	
② 2962	8825
6628	11309
③ 17946	
SAT 1 SAT 2	
② 3452	② 2854
6535	5565
8861	11291
③ 13357	③ 13315
③ 17955	③ 17955
VHF	
① 119.30	① 126.50
① 129.10	① 130.90
① 133.00	
SELCAL	

3200m HORTA 4000m (1600m LATER)

475m HORTA 5000m (1600m LATER)

610m HORTA 6000m (1600m LATER)

① SATCOM Air-to-Ground COM-Failure.

IRKID N33 55.5 W018 04.2 PEL N33 26.7 W018 04.2 (Not required) N33 28.9 W018 04.2

ABALO N32 19.9 W018 07.8 NELSO N31 41.0 W017 27.4

TENKO N30 43.4 W013 53.3

ROSTA N28 15.4 W020 00.0

B034: ITOP – Interception of processed North American pollution to the east of the Azores and contrasting African air.

Mission Scientists: Paul S Monks and Ally Lewis

Date: 25/7/04

Outline schedule:

06:00 UT - Power to aircraft - Warm-up

08:00 UT - Air Crew Briefing

09:15 UT – Security sweep

09:30 UT – Boarding deadline

10:00 UT - Take-off

Location: Working in a box bordered from the TMA and 36 24 N, 20W; 37N 30W; 31N, 30W; 31N, 20W (Surface to FL 250).

Aim: To intercept extensive layers of polluted air between surface and FL220 that left US domain 5 days ago, they have been torn from the main W-E flow and flung further south. Possible opportunities to intercept layers of air sampled by the NASA DC8 on 20/07/04. Exploration of contrasting air of continental African origin. If time, sampling of air near Pico will be made, for comparison with surface observations.

Sortie Detail

1. T+0 Take Off. Ascend to first available level for wet chemistry checks. (10)
2. T+10 En-route ascent to FL130 and run to ETROX (36 24N, 24 W) (70).
3. T+80 Head towards 34.5 N 20W, profile ascent to FL220 at 1000ft/min (10)
4. T+90 10 minute straight and level run at FL220 (10)
5. T+ 100 Profile descent to @ 1000ft/min until 5,000ft then 500ft/min to 100ft (30)
6. T+130, Profile ascent to 5,000ft at 500ft/min running to 34.5 N 19W (20)
7. T+150 Spiral ascent at 34.5 N 19W at 1,000ft/min to FL320 (if possible), breaking for 2 10 minute runs on a north-south heading (50)
8. T+200 Turn and head towards ETROX taking three levels for runs (FL320, FL250, FL 180) (70)
9. T+270 Head to Santa Maria (20)
10. T +290 Land at Santa Maria, for refuel (need ground power for instruments) (20)
11. T+0 Take-off, climb to FL150 for run to Horta
12. T+60 NNE Pico fly-by at 7,200ft for a 3 minute straight and level run, followed by 3 minute runs at 6,000ft and 5,000ft. (15)
13. T+75 Land at Horta.

CALIBRATIONS POST FLIGHT 1034

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...034.....

Date25/07/2004.....

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START Pos'n

Video Tapes			GPS	INU		DRS ☒
V8						
No.			Lat	38 31.26N		
Ends			Long	28 42.98W	As SR	HORACE ☒
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC			Time	09 40 51	←	SATCOM ☒
			Status	✓		

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
		HORACE crash in preflight						
09 40 50		INU → NAV						
09 50 58		TAXI						
09 56 48		T/O from Horta						
10 00 20		ASPs open						
10 08 10		PSAP flow on						
10 12 50		end J-W zero cal						
10 13 57		TWC reset						
10 15 07		video recording starts.						
10 15 50		HORACE crash						
10 17 00		Cabin temp +21.3°C 20.7% RH (at HORACE position)						
10 26 20	- 10 27 50	HORACE running, but data stopped recording? nothing shows in DRS log file. All derived data at zero during this time.						
		DLU configuration - error messages (Invalid port address) for PRTAFT DLU						
10 48 50		SATCOM H call, CCM → JFE						
11 03 18		cabin temp +19.4°C 14.8% RH						
11 23 00		- " - +19.0°C 10.7% RH						
12 00 50		Satcom H, CCM → JFE						
12 38 00		- " - +20.7°C 19.2% RH						
12 59 40		PSAP flow off						
13 02 10		PSAP flow on						
13 03 55		PSAP flow off						
13 04 20		PSAP flow on						
13 05 35		PSAP flow off						

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B.....034.....

Date25/7/04.....

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Video Tapes
V8
No.
Ends
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	35 42.68N	35 43.41N
Long	22 55.91W	22 57.13W
Time	14:30:24	14:30:57
Status	✓	✓

DRS	☒
HORACE	☒
SATCOM	☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
13 07 55	PSAP flow on			FFC	observed -	ice on	wind	
13 10 19	PSAP flow off							
13 12 48	PSAP flow on							
13 13 38	PSAP flow off							
13 14 48	PSAP flow on							
13 17 20	PSAP flow off							
13 18 50	PSAP flow on							
13 24 07	PSAP flow off							
13 24 51	PSAP flow on							
13 26 15	PSAP flow off			hot air to camera				
13 26 30	PSAP flow on							
13 33 00	PSAP flow off							
~ 13 36 00	PSAP flow on							
~ 13 37 27	PSAP flow on			tail icing off, FFC still still iced up				
13 46 00	PSAP flow on							
13 50 00	FFC improved vision, still some large patches of ice							
14 28 00	SATCOM H call, ECM → DR							
14 45 50	Cabin temp +18.9°C 10-0% RH (top HORACE)							
~ 14 40 00	SATCOM H, Ali → John Methuen							
~ 14 50 00	— " — Paul Mowles → DR							
15:08:38	Land Sta. Maria			ASPs open				
15 12:30	Stop, Sta. Maria			GPS posn: 36 58.46N		25 09.96 W		
15 14 42				INU posn 36 57.86N		25 09.38 W		
15 15 40	IND → GC Algin							

Flight Manager's In-Flight Log

Flight No B...034

Date 25/7/2004

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pre-Taxi; Sta Maria.

Video Tapes		GPS	INU	DRS ☒
V8		Lat	36 58.46 W	
No.		Long	25 09.96 W	HORACE ☒
Ends		Time	16 07 20	
FFC / RFC / DFC / UFC		Status	✓4	SATCOM ☒

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
16 19 57		ASPs closed						
16 20 20		INU → at Nav						
16 38 00		Taxi						
16 39 49		T/O, Santa Maria						
16 42 40		PSAP flow on				QNH		Punta Delgado = 1021 hPa
16 49 05	}	Jw calibration						
16 51 05								
16 53 40		videos on						
17 34 15		PSAP flow off						
17 37 15		PSAP flow on						
17 57 10		PSAP flow off						
17 58 10		PSAP flow on						
≈ 17 58 00		SATCOM, Paul → Horta scientific						
18 40 25		PSAP flow off						
18 42 00		PSAP flow on						
18 49 15		PSAP flow off						
18 53 46		Land at Horta						
18 57 22		final GPS posn:		38	31.26 W	28 42.98 W		
18 :58 :00		final INU posn:		38	31.26 N	28 43.66 W		

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B034

Instruments

HORACE crashes 1 preflight
1 during flight

No RADALT data

Loss of derived data between 10 26 20 - 10 27 50
(approx. times).

Not noticed until data being correctly displayed
again, when HORACE reported that data was
being recorded and the flight number was correct.
Nothing obviously wrong in the DRS log file.

In DLU configuration: error messages (invalid port address)
for PRTACT DLU.

Aircraft